

EXPERTISE

What is your area of expertise and what are the findings you want to convey?

What skills do you have to impart your knowledge?

What external skills and expertise are required?

IMPACT PROPOSITION

Why are/is your scientific findings/knowledge relevant for your target group?

What is the value you that you will generate for your target groups?

Which overarching societal questions does your impact proposition address?

TARGET GROUP

Who do you aim to reach with your impact proposition?

Why are they the primary target group for your impact proposition?

Are there any secondary target groups?

Who else would be (positively or negatively) affected by your impact proposition?

FORMAT

Which format is best suited for addressing your target group?

Why is this format the most feasible / suitable one?

How does the choice of format affect the knowledge sharing?

CHANNEL

What channel is most suitable for distributing your impact proposition?

Why is this channel the best for your choice of format?

How will the choice of channel affect the impact proposition?

STRATEGIC OPPORTUNITY

What are the boundary conditions for your impact proposition?

What are trends, events and current debates that you need to consider?

When is the best time to realize your project?

RESOURCES

What resources (e.g. team, material, space, services) are needed to realize your project?

What resources are most important and why?

Which of these resources are at your disposal?

CORE ACTIVITIES

Which activities are necessary to realize your project?

What activities are most important ones and why?

Which of these activities can you manage yourself and where do you need support?

COLLABORATORS

Who can you collaborate with in order to realize your project?

What can they add to the impact proposition and / or the execution of your project?

Why should they collaborate with you?

COSTS

What are the costs of implementing your impact proposition?

How justified are the costs in relation to the intended effect and in relation to each other?

FUNDING

Where will you get the funds to realize your project?

Will the funding affect the impact proposition?

Why should the funder fund your project?

BENEFIT

How will you benefit?

How will your organization benefit?

SUCCESS INDICATORS

What would make your undertaking a success?

What are the relevant indicators for measuring success?

Are there any difficulties in measuring or evaluating success?

RISKS

How could the project negatively affect you or your organization?

Which negative effects could your project have on other stakeholders?